

Taking a Walk on the Wild Side: Effects of Walking in Synchrony with Pitch-Altered Footstep Sounds on Body Perception in Outside the Lab Contexts

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Figure 1: a) Study setup composed of headphones, smartphone and accelerometer, b) Sound filters and conditions used to process the footstep soundtracks, c) The experiment area where participants walked while synchronizing to the footstep soundtracks.

Abstract

The 'Footsteps Illusion' shows that pitch-altering footstep sounds in real-time affects body perception, gait, and emotion: high versus low frequencies evoke a lighter versus heavier body. We tested whether this illusion extends beyond the lab, where environmental factors

matter. Using a mixed-methods approach, twenty-eight participants used a minimal setup to synchronize with three prerecorded pitch-altered footstep soundtracks: Control, High-Frequency, and Low-Frequency. In Experiment 1, they walked a fixed path, with gait recordings, questionnaires, and body visualizations. In Experiment 2, they walked freely across campus routes with High/Low-Frequency soundtracks, followed by post-walk interviews using a novel spatial mapping tool linking body sensations to context. Results replicate the illusion outdoors, showing synchronization with prerecorded sounds as a viable alternative to real-time feedback, and revealing that contextual factors modulate illusion effects. We contribute insights and novel tools (prototype, spatial mapping method, and footstep soundbase) for studying multisensory body perception in everyday contexts.

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CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → **User studies; Empirical studies in HCI; Auditory feedback**; • **Applied computing** → *Psychology*.

Keywords

Auditory Body Perception; Multimodal Interfaces; Sonification; Mixed Methods; Emotion; Evaluation Method; Embodied Interaction, Wearable Computers

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1 Introduction

Body perception is a complex phenomenon encompassing both perceptual components (e.g., perceived body size) and attitudinal aspects (e.g., emotional responses and thoughts about one's body size) [30]. These elements influence motor [20], emotional [99, 118], and social functioning [6, 21, 132]. Importantly, neuroscience studies have shown that multisensory stimulation involving the body can significantly reshape body perception [12, 70, 149]. With the emergence and advancement of body sensing and actuating technologies, it is now possible to design multisensory systems that influence and modify body perception [7, 63, 65, 68, 87, 94, 97, 121, 149, 150], and in turn affect emotional states, cognitive processes, and behavior [21, 30, 139]. This opens new avenues for research on body perception and potential applications in diverse fields, including health, sports, entertainment, and the arts.

One such multisensory system was introduced by [139]: a wearable device that modifies, in real-time, the wearer's footstep sounds to alter the perceived body weight, and in turn gait and emotional experience. This 'Footsteps Illusion' has since been explored across multiple application contexts [16, 21, 24, 35, 50, 140, 141, 144]. While earlier studies on the Footsteps Illusion have primarily focused on controlled laboratory environments, they leave open the question of how contextual and environmental factors shape the illusion in everyday life, where walking surfaces, spatial constraints, and social presence cannot be controlled. Understanding how footstep sounds affect body perception in real-world contexts can therefore provide new insights into the interaction between multisensory feedback and environmental variability. Such contexts introduce additional factors that may modulate the strength and nature of the illusion. However, extending studies of the Footsteps Illusion beyond the lab is not straightforward. Previous versions of the systems used to facilitate the illusion relied on microphones to capture participants' real-time footstep sounds and alter them on the fly [16, 21, 24, 35, 50, 139–141]. However, these microphones also pick up surrounding environmental sounds, making it difficult to deploy the system in everyday settings. This limitation highlights the need for alternative approaches. Recent research suggests a potential solution: coordinating actions with externally produced

footstep sounds (e.g., sounds of other people walking) can alter how individuals feel and perceive their own bodies [40]. Building on this insight, in this study we investigate whether the effects of the Footsteps Illusion on perceived body weight can also be elicited when participants synchronize with prerecorded auditory cues, rather than relying on real-time feedback, offering a first step towards bringing this phenomenon outside the lab and into real-world contexts with a simpler set-up.

In this work, participants were asked to synchronize their walking with prerecorded footstep sounds, replicating the same spectral manipulations as in previous works [24], utilizing a high frequency (HF) and a low frequency (LF) filter. Building on recent work highlighting the importance of mixed-methods approaches to studying bodily experience [109], we conducted two experiments integrating quantitative (Experiment 1) and qualitative (Experiment 2) measures, while also bridging insights from cognitive neuroscience with design research and HCI.

In Experiment 1, participants walked back and forth along an outdoor linear passage, which was part of the university campus, while synchronizing with the prerecorded footstep sounds. Using self-report and behavioral measures (i.e., gait and body visualization), we tested the hypothesis that frequency manipulations of the sounds would replicate earlier laboratory findings: participants would perceive their bodies as lighter and slimmer in HF compared to LF. We also measured whether participants actually synchronized with the footstep sounds and whether they felt agency over the sounds, as previous studies have shown that significant disparities between modalities or delays in action-feedback reduce sensory-induced body illusions [84, 149]. Experiment 2 is a qualitative study conducted in a larger campus area outdoors, with diverse surfaces, where contextual factors such as terrain, weather, and the presence of other people could not be controlled. Here, we hypothesized that environmental and contextual variability would modulate the illusion, influencing synchronization, agency, and body perception. To capture these situated experiences, we designed a novel spatial mapping tool that enabled participants to reflect on their routes, annotate body sensations with stickers, and use colors, arrows, and symbols to describe their embodied experiences. Together, these two experiments allowed us to test the robustness of the Footsteps Illusion in real-world environments.

This study presents three main contributions:

- Evidence showing that the effects on perceived body weight, and its related effects on body behavior and emotional experience, reported in studies with the Footsteps Illusion can be elicited when participants synchronize with prerecorded pitch-altered footstep sounds, rather than relying on real-time feedback.
- A novel prototype, allowing a minimal and portable version of the Footsteps Illusion, which enables studies outside the lab in different contexts, opening new research questions, such as the influence of contextual factors.
- Insights on how contextual factors present outside the lab, such as the type of surface a person walks on or the presence of other people, interact with sound in shaping body perception and user experience.

Additionally, our paper presents two smaller contributions: a novel spatial mapping tool (i.e., a landscape map) consisting of context-sensitive body maps anchored in the environment, which help capture relationships between body and environment; and a database (see Supplementary material¹) of prerecorded footstep sounds, which can be utilized as a resource for other applications, i.e., sound design and virtual reality.

Our work extends prior HCI research on interactive sound and body perception, which has largely focused on body sonification (e.g., [8, 15, 41, 42, 48, 51, 53, 72, 73, 76, 86, 104, 105, 123, 125, 128, 159, 161]) by showing the potential of prerecorded sounds to produce similar perceptual effects, and highlights the role of contextual factors in shaping how people experience both sound and their own bodies. Together, these contributions open new avenues for designing and studying sound-based body transformation experiences in everyday settings, with potential implications for health and well-being, sports, entertainment, and the arts.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 Interactive Systems to Change Body Perception/Interactive Systems for Body Transformation Experiences

Interactive systems have been developed to induce Body Transformation Experiences [162], or perceptual illusions of changes in one's own body. Examples include illusions of having a longer arm [64], a shorter/taller or slimmer/wider body [87, 97, 166], embodying a child's body [138], or embodying different physical attributes [5, 91]. These experiences are typically achieved through Virtual Reality [64, 97, 138], full body-swapping using head-mounted displays [7, 87, 94, 166], or video-based face-swapping with another person (the so-called enfacement illusion [121, 145, 156]). Such techniques have been used to investigate changes in social attitudes, for instance when embodying people with a different skin tone [5, 80, 91] or gender [132, 133], as well as changes in own body perception, such as size [64, 138, 166] or weight [97]. These latter studies further demonstrate associated effects on behavior [87, 166] and emotion [100, 101]. The key to these Body Transformation Experiences is the alteration of immediate bodily sensory feedback, as explained below.

2.1.1 Malleability of Body Perception. Neuroscience research has shown that body perception is highly malleable and shaped by sensory signals (i.e., those arising from vision, hearing, touch, and other modalities). Within seconds of multisensory stimulation, people may perceive dummy limbs [12], tools [81], or virtual bodies [64, 138] as part of their own body. Such updates in body perception enable us to remain aware of, and adapt to, the positioning and movement of our body parts, as well as to our continuously changing physical appearance and dimensions [28]. Beyond this kinesthetic role, body perception is also influenced by cognitive factors (e.g., prior beliefs about one's body and social perception [3, 6, 11, 33, 43]) and affective or emotional processes (including self-concept and self-esteem [21, 99, 132, 145]). For instance, when we feel happy, we may experience our bodies as

lighter and more agile, whereas sadness can make us perceive them as heavier [52].

2.1.2 Researching Body Perception through Mixed Methods. Bodily experience is inherently complex, arising from the interplay of sensory, cognitive, affective, and contextual factors rather than a single dimension. This complexity is evident in the frequent dissociations between subjective reports, behavioral, and physiological indices [1, 112, 154], highlighting the limitations of any one method alone. Advancing research in HCI on body perception requires acknowledging its multidimensional and nuanced character and employing methodological approaches that are not only complementary but necessary: combining qualitative methods from design research centered on body experiences, with quantitative approaches from neuroscience and psychology, enables richer accounts, gaining explanations of subjective bodily experiences, and supports the design of interactive systems that shape body perception. This mixed-methods perspective fosters multidisciplinary exchange and helps bridge HCI with design, the social sciences and the arts [109]. Successful applications of mixed-methods approaches in body perception research involving sound already demonstrate the value of combining qualitative and quantitative perspectives across design research in HCI and cognitive science (e.g., [110, 125]). Building on this approach, we adopt a mixed-methods design, conducting two experiments that together combine quantitative and qualitative methods to study body perception, drawing from cognitive neuroscience, HCI, and design research.

2.2 Shaping Body Perception With Sound

Auditory feedback strongly influences the perception of one's body and its surrounding space [127, 148, 150]. Numerous studies have shown that sound feedback can alter body perception, including the perceived length of limbs—such as arms [146, 149], legs [148], and fingers [85, 108, 137]—as well as their material properties, as demonstrated by the marble hand illusion [119] and the parchment-skin illusion [56]. Sound feedback has also been used to modify full-body weight perception [24, 139], as explained in the next section. Importantly, these studies further show that individuals adapt their behavior in response to altered body perceptions—for example, by changing how they perform reaching movements [134, 143] or physical exercises [71, 124]. Moreover, auditory manipulations can be used to evoke distinct emotional responses related to the body and its movements [71–74, 86, 123, 125].

We note that there is a rich body of work in HCI on designing and evaluating body sonification experiences, where body movements are detected and mapped onto sound. These approaches have been applied across diverse domains, including skill learning and sports [8, 9, 53, 88, 114, 115, 128, 167], artistic and expressive practices such as dance, aerial acrobatics, and performance [34, 41, 42, 51, 58, 76, 92, 93, 163], rehabilitation and health, including physiotherapy and chronic pain [48, 86, 114, 116, 117, 125, 169], everyday activities and fitness [71, 73, 74, 122, 123, 161], as well as somaesthetic appreciation and musical interaction [104, 105, 171]. However, these works primarily focus on providing feedback on one's *actual* body or its movements, typically through sounds that the body does not naturally produce. In contrast, in this paper we focus on the effects of providing *altered* body stimuli, specifically

¹<https://osf.io/t7udq>

using sounds that resemble those the body naturally produces, to explore their impact on body perception, and related behavior and emotional experience.

2.2.1 Changing Perceived Body Weight through Footstep Sounds: the Footsteps Illusion. The Footsteps Illusion was first described in [139], where a wearable system modified footstep sounds in real-time, as people walked, to influence perceived body weight. By lowering or heightening the spectral components of the sounds, the system creates 'Low Frequency' (LF) and 'High Frequency' (HF) versions of the captured footsteps sounds (i.e., pitch-altered footstep sounds), corresponding to heavier or lighter bodies (see also [75, 153], where spectral manipulations of walking sounds influenced the perceived body characteristics of another person). Using self-report, behavioral, and physiological measures, results [139] showed that short-term exposure to these pitch-altered sounds modified participants' perceived body size and weight, with HF sounds leading to lighter/slimmer body perceptions and more dynamic gait patterns resembling those observed in lighter bodies [155, 164]. The illusion was also linked to emotional changes, with HF footsteps associated with increased happiness. Other manipulations of footstep sounds have been shown to influence gait [15, 84, 158], though these effects were not connected to changes in body perception. Follow-up studies extended the illusion to gender identity (with HF increasing feelings of femininity [21, 24, 144]), exercise support [144], chronic pain and stroke rehabilitation [50, 140], and the study of eating disorders [141], while also revealing cross-modal effects with olfaction [16].

The original system relied on an analog equalizer and shoe-mounted microphones, but was later digitized into the more portable *SoniWeight Shoes* [24, 27], which still used shoe-mounted microphones to capture footsteps. This version enabled studies with larger samples (100+ participants) and opened avenues for personalization [24] by examining individual differences (e.g., eating disorders, physical activity levels) and the role of social factors in the illusion [35]. Together, this body of work demonstrates the potential of the Footsteps Illusion to modulate body perception, emotional experience, and behavior. However, all prior studies have been conducted in controlled environments. Extending this paradigm to real-life contexts poses significant challenges, as the reliance on microphones also captures environmental noise, limiting ecological validity, and highlighting the need for alternative approaches. To this end, we developed a minimal system that can be deployed outside the lab, enabling exploration of the Footsteps Illusion across diverse contexts and use cases.

2.3 Synchronizing Sensorimotor Signals: Body Perception and Agency

Neuroscientific research has identified key principles for altering body perception through sensory feedback: (1) feedback should resemble naturalistic bodily cues (semantic congruency), (2) be temporally synchronized with sensory or motor cues (temporal congruency), (3) be spatially aligned with the body (spatial congruency), and (4) be attributed to one's own actions (agency and ownership) [62, 63, 77, 157]. While some of these principles have been challenged—for instance, the principle of semantic congruency in studies using non-naturalistic sound cues [85, 108, 137]—agency

remains central when movement is involved, as in the Footsteps Illusion. Agency arises from the tight coupling between movements and their sensory consequences (temporal congruency). For example, delaying auditory feedback from footsteps has been shown to disrupt the sense of self-generated action, reducing both agency and body ownership [84]. The same study [84] also reported a modest reduction in agency within a relatively broad temporal window (16–100 ms), in which feedback is still perceived as self-generated. Additionally, prior work on gait synchronization demonstrates that people can efficiently entrain to external rhythmic cues, and still experience them as aligned with their own actions [102]. These findings suggest that agency does not require perfectly real-time feedback, but rather feedback that is predictable and rhythmically aligned with the person's actions. Based on this theoretical foundation, prerecorded footstep sounds can preserve a sense of agency when participants synchronize their walking to the audio stream, because the temporal predictability and stable phase relationship between steps and sound remain within the tolerance thresholds that support sensorimotor coupling.

HCI research further supports this: motion-coupled vibrotactile feedback in shoes or mid-air haptics creates compelling illusions only when bound to user movements [31, 130, 131]. Electrical muscle stimulation studies also emphasize the interplay between body perception and agency [57]. Together, these findings show that bodily illusions depend critically on participants perceiving their actions as self-generated (i.e., agency).

Building on this, the present study asks whether participants can maintain agency while synchronizing with prerecorded footstep sounds to elicit the Footsteps Illusion. This draws on [40], which examined how self-other integration and segregation shape coordination and self-awareness during group interactions. Participants synchronized their footsteps with a metronome while hearing virtual partners' footsteps. Measures of temporal coordination (step timing regularity and synchrony with the metronome), see [32, 61, 106], gait patterns, and subjective experience (sense of self, group cohesion) showed that coordination was strongest when participants heard distinct yet synchronous footsteps, which enhanced agency, strength, dominance, and happiness. This work demonstrates that individuals can reliably synchronize movements with auditory cues and that hearing footsteps—even attributed to others—can alter bodily states and emotional experience. Synchronization tasks are also established in body illusion research: in [142], participants synchronized face-stroking with a model, eliciting changes in self-recognition (the 'enfacement illusion'). Together, these studies suggest that synchronization with sensory cues—even prerecorded or externally attributed—can reliably induce changes in body perception and associated emotional experience.

2.4 Body and Space: Contextualizing Body Experience

HCI research has examined the interaction between environment and bodily experiences. For instance, [152] designed a wearable device that captures and amplifies the sound of footsteps, emphasizing the interplay between a walker and their urban environment. The device invites users to interact with various surfaces—i.e., metal

grates, gravel, and marble steps—transforming walking into an exploratory and auditory experience. Similarly, in the work by [59], participants followed maps of city areas on foot to explore auditory paths created by the acoustic properties of different urban materials. A related approach is used in soundwalks: participants follow a route on a map, stop at different points to listen to the environment, and rate their auditory experience [171]. Extending this, [159] employed a system to alter footstep sounds in real-time and provide the illusion of wearing different shoe types and walking on different ground materials (e.g., wood, gravel, snow), showing how footstep sounds are shaped by various combinations of shoe type and ground materials, and paving the way to design ecologically-valid auditory rendering of foot-floor interactions. Overall, these studies underscore the role of environmental and material contexts in shaping perception.

Research by [78] describes how environments—whether oppressive, liberating, or precarious—physically shape experiences of the body, showing that lived experiences are shaped by external factors, suggesting that including spatial, social, and contextual factors is important to understanding how body perception evolves in real-world settings. Indeed, beyond physical context, social factors also modulate body experience. Recent work using the Footsteps Illusion found that individuals with smaller social support networks were more susceptible to changes in body perception, while larger networks correlated with greater body image satisfaction and fewer eating disorder symptoms [35]. Together, these findings emphasize that body perception is dynamically shaped not only by sensory cues but also by material and social environments. To capture such dynamics, body maps [2, 160] have been adapted to reflect both narrative contexts and embodied actions. In [47], authors emphasized contextualizing body maps within narrative frameworks, i.e., storytelling methodologies, integrating environmental, social, and temporal elements to gain richer appreciation of how external factors influence bodily states and emotional experiences. The work by [73] also modified body maps to depict bodies engaged in specific movements to grasp experiences in their corresponding actions. Drawing from the work by [4], that used outdoor area maps to document, analyze, and design interactive play systems within residential areas, we combine body maps with outdoor area maps (landscape maps), to capture felt sensations across the body and space, attending to contextual influences such as surfaces, weather, and social interactions. Our research extends work on the dynamic relationship between body and space by investigating these interactions through the Footsteps Illusion, situating body perception within the broader interplay of spatial, social, and material contexts [30, 78, 139].

3 Experiment 1

Experiment 1 was designed as a quantitative study to investigate how synchronizing walking with prerecorded frequency-modulated footstep sounds delivered through headphones affects body perception in an outdoor setting. The experiment aimed to systematically measure these effects through behavioral and self-report data.

3.1 Methods

3.1.1 Participants. 28 participants naïve to the research aim took part in the study, but four were excluded from Experiment 1 due to excessive noise in the data, leaving 24 participants (mean age \pm SD: 27.04 ± 10.53 years, range: 20-71; sex: 12 males and 12 females; gender: 12 masculine and 12 feminine; mean weight \pm SD: 66.42 ± 11.30 kg; mean height \pm SD: 170.12 ± 8.76 cm), who were recruited through the Universidad Carlos III de Madrid participant pool, public advertisements, social networking sites, and flyers. Inclusion criteria were: age over 18 years; normal hearing; no disabling orthopedic or neuromuscular conditions affecting walking; proficiency in Spanish or English; and the ability to understand study information, provide informed consent, and communicate effectively. Participants provided the following information during recruitment: demographics, including age, sex (man, woman, non-binary, decline to state), gender (masculine, feminine, non-binary person, decline to state); and anthropometric measurements (height and weight). The latter were used for the body visualizer task (see section 3.1.4) and to select the appropriate footsteps soundtrack used in the study. They also filled in the Spanish versions of the following questionnaires, not analyzed in this paper: the Betts' Questionnaire on Mental Imagery [19] and the Questionnaire on Social Support Networks [83] (see section 3.1.4). The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards laid down in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and its later amendments and was approved by the Committee of Ethics in Research of Universidad Carlos III de Madrid. All participants provided informed consent before participating and received a €20 bank transfer as compensation for their time.

3.1.2 Apparatus and Materials. The setup consisted of an Android smartphone (LG Nexus 5), used to reproduce the footsteps audio files, and a pair of headphones (Sennheiser HDA300) with high passive ambient noise attenuation (>30 dBA). Participants were asked to wear comfortable sports shoes and clothing. Gait acceleration was recorded with a Bitalino PLUX acquisition system (8-Channel biosignalsplux hub) at a sampling rate of 1000 Hz, using an accelerometer placed on the participants' right ankle. We focused on data from the right foot since we did not have any specific hypothesis on left/right asymmetries [147]. Importantly, whereas previous studies [16, 21, 24, 139, 140, 144] employed a real-time footstep sound modification system, the present study used prerecorded sounds, as described below.

Soundtracks Design: to obtain the final audio files that each participant listens during the walk, a three-steps process was followed, as depicted in Figure 2.

Footstep Sounds Recording: footstep sounds were recorded in an anechoic chamber; see Figure 3 a), using microphones positioned both at the walkers' ears and shoes. The recording design incorporated different surfaces, i.e., wood (MDF) and marble tiles, see Figure 3 c), footwear, i.e., leather dress shoes (EU sizes 42 and 46) and hard rubber-soled sandals (EU size 42 only, adjustable to accommodate larger feet), and subjects: three individuals weighing approximately 50, 60 and 70 kg. Each subject completed eight recording sessions covering all combinations of surfaces and footwear. To simulate a broader range of body weights (50-80 kg), during these recordings, the subjects performed these sessions both with and without

Figure 2: Soundtracks Design: process followed to obtain the final audio files that each participant listens to during the walks. After recording the footstep sounds, the soundtracks generation phase involved: cutting and randomizing the footstep pairs (C & R), applying the filters to obtain the sound conditions (LF, C, HF EQ) and setting the soundtracks SNR after adding the recorded background noise. The final soundtracks selected were those generated with shoe microphones, at 100 bpm, with sandals on MDF and with an SNR of 0 dB.

additional 5-kg fitness weights, allowing to gather sound recordings for the following weight ranges: 50-55 kg, 55-60 kg, 60-65 kg, 65-70 kg, 70-75 kg, and 75-80 kg. To prevent footstep pace changes during the recordings, walkers synchronized their steps using a visual smartphone metronome to avoid any additional sound. Each session consisted of five one-minute phases: walking in place and walking normally at 80 bpm, walking in place and walking normally at 100 bpm, and walking in place at 120 bpm. Normal walking at 120 bpm was excluded from recording, as the available path length in the anechoic chamber (4.8 m) would have necessitated unnaturally short steps.

Soundtracks Generation: following the anechoic recordings, a collection of individual footstep sounds was extracted from the recordings, for each of the recording conditions. With this, for each combination of recording variables, a continuous five-minute audio sequence of randomized footstep sounds was constructed. This randomization of steps was conducted to obtain natural walking sounds with natural step variations, hereafter referred to as soundtracks. Then, after obtaining a soundtrack, and consistent with prior literature [16, 21, 24, 139, 140, 144], three spectral filtering were applied to it: HF, amplifying 1–4 kHz components and attenuating 83–250 Hz by 12 dB; LF, amplifying 83–250 Hz and attenuating above 1 kHz by 12 dB; and C, a flat frequency response maintaining natural footstep characteristics. To simulate realistic acoustic scenes, we recorded ambient background noise at the experiment site in which the tests would be performed rather than relying on generic public databases. This background noise, which was devoid of distinct salient acoustic events, was mixed with the generated footstep soundtrack (i.e., for the HF, LF, and C conditions) at four Signal-To-Noise Ratios (SNR): 0, 5, 10, and 15 dB. During this process, the three spectral versions of the soundtracks were loudness matched (in terms of A-weighted energy) which, in return, ensured a constant SNR between the steps in each of them and the background noise.

Soundtracks Selection: a piloting session was conducted at the experiment location to select the footstep soundtracks for the final study. Choices were made considering all variables, i.e., recordings at different positions (walkers' shoes or ears), walking at different speeds (80, 100, or 120 bpm), on different surface materials (MDF

wood or marble), with different footwear, and across the four SNR levels. This session assessed the plausibility of the generated soundtracks—whether they resembled the participants' own footsteps (matched to their body weight) and whether they blended realistically with the acoustic and environmental context. The selected soundtracks, recorded with microphones on the walkers' shoes and walking normally at 100 bpm, was 'sandals on wood', with an SNR of 0 dB, which recreated a natural level of background noise and sounded the most realistic in that specific outdoor setting. See Supplementary Material and [25] for a detailed description of the recording and piloting procedures.

3.1.3 Experiment Design. A within-subjects experimental design was used, in which participants experienced three sound conditions (HF, LF, C) in randomized order. Condition randomization served to discard differences due to practice. The dependent variables were the outcome measures described in the next section. The setup is shown in Figure 1.

3.1.4 Outcome Measures. We measured whether participants could effectively synchronize with the heard footstep sounds, as this is a prerequisite for the Footsteps Illusion to emerge, as well as measured potential differences in coordination across sound conditions. Then, to assess the effects of auditory feedback on bodily and emotional experience, we used self-reports and behavioral measures, as described below. With respect to emotional experience, we focused on the subjective experience of emotions [26], characterized by valence, arousal, and dominance, in line with dimensional theories of emotion (e.g., [66, 113]). Participants also filled out paper body maps after each sound condition, to indicate changes in body sensations or perceptions, following [24], although these results are not reported here.

Synchronization and Coordination To accurately calculate synchronization values, we implemented a custom setup designed to align the timing of the gait cycle events with the audio track. An Android application was developed to trigger the smartphone's vibration every time the footstep soundtrack began or ended. A secondary accelerometer was positioned directly behind the smartphone, close to its vibration motor, ensuring that the vibrations could be reliably detected. This configuration allowed the vibration signal to serve as a timestamp marker for the soundtrack onset and offset. During each data acquisition, the Bitalino device simultaneously recorded: ankle acceleration data (capturing the participant's gait movements) and smartphone vibration data (capturing precise timing of the audio events). By identifying the vibration patterns within the smartphone accelerometer signal, we were able to synchronize the ankle acceleration data with the exact start time of the soundtrack. For an illustration of this setup, see Figure 3 d).

Synchronization measures were assessed by calculating the asynchronies between the participant's footsteps and both the prerecorded footstep soundtrack and a 100 bpm metronome matching the tempo used during the recordings, followed by computing the standard deviation (SD) for each condition. Lower SD asynchrony is indicative of greater coupling. Then, to measure coordination, for each participant, we extracted each inter-step-interval (ISI) and then calculated the SD. We used SD ISI, a measure of step timing regularity where a lower SD ISI is assumed to reflect the agent's focus on producing a consistent signal [39, 40, 107].

Figure 3: a) Footstep sounds recording session. b) A participant walking and synchronizing to the footsteps prerecorded sounds. c) Footstep soundtracks. Six soundtracks were created to cover different body-weight ranges. Piloting sessions were conducted to select the soundtracks. These were recorded at different locations (walker's shoes or ears), produced while walking at different speeds (80, 100 or 120 bpm), on different surface materials (MDF wood or marble) and with different types of footwear. d) Sound delivery and gait acquisition.

Questionnaire on Body Feelings and Emotional Experience: A Likert-type questionnaire (see Supplementary Material), adapted from [24, 139, 144], was used to assess body feelings. Nine statements addressed felt walking speed (*Quickness*), body weight (*Weight*), *Strength*, posture (*Straightness*), and femininity/masculinity (*Masculinity*), *Experience Vividness*, *Surprise*, *Agency* over sounds [84, 149], and foot localization (*Proprioception*) [149]. Construct validity for this measure is supported by prior studies on the Footsteps Illusion, where the same items have been used to capture participants' bodily experiences [16, 24, 139–141, 144].

Emotional experience was assessed with the Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM) questionnaire [13], comprising three 9-point graphic scales for *Valence*, *Arousal*, and *Dominance*. Widely used to evaluate emotional responses to acoustic stimuli [14], the SAM has also been applied in previous studies on the Footsteps Illusion [16, 24, 139–141, 144]. This ensures that the measure reliably captures the intended emotional constructs in the context of our study.

Body Visualization: Participants' visual estimates of their body weight were assessed using the Body Visualizer tool [98]. This measure has been used in previous Footsteps Illusion studies, supporting its construct validity [16, 24, 139–141, 144]. Using this tool allows for an explicit assessment of participants' perceived body size (see also [96]), consistent with earlier work in this research area. As in previous works, after each trial, participants completed the task twice. The experimenter set the avatar's gender and height to match those of the participant and initialized its weight at either 85% or 115% of the participant's actual weight. Using keyboard arrows, participants adjusted the avatar's 'weight' dimension to match their perceived body size (see [24, 139, 141, 144]). The initial weight condition was counterbalanced across trials to avoid anchoring effects of the starting value [96, 139], and analyses used the average estimate for each sound condition.

Gait Biomechanics: Gait measures were used as an implicit behavioral index of changes in perceived body weight. Previous work

has shown that gait parameters are modulated by body weight [155, 164], and studies on the Footsteps Illusion have demonstrated that sound manipulations consistent with lighter or heavier bodies lead participants to adjust their gait toward the prototypical gait pattern of those bodies [16, 24, 139, 141, 144]; thus, features of gait biomechanics serve as a valid behavioral index of perceived body weight. As in those studies, we quantified foot acceleration and time parameters for each gait cycle (i.e., the time between two successive steps of the same foot) [23].

3.1.5 Procedure. Figure 4 shows a graphical overview of the experimental procedure. Participants were pre-screened based on demographics and asked to answer the questionnaires on social support networks, and imaginary vividness.

The experiment consisted of four two-minute trials. Each trial involved walking in place for 10 seconds and then walking back and forth once along a linear passage approximately 50 meters in length while synchronizing to the footstep soundtracks; see Figure 3 b). During each trial, movement data from the accelerometer placed on the ankle were acquired.

Participants first completed a practice trial (C) to familiarize themselves with the experimental tasks. They then completed the HF, LF and C trials in randomized order. At the end of each trial, participants performed the body visualization task and filled in the questionnaire on body feelings and emotional experiences, and the body maps.

3.1.6 Statistical Analyses and Data Treatment. Gait and audio data were processed in MATLAB (version R2022a). Acceleration signals were plotted and peaks and valleys were extracted to determine peak acceleration and duration of the various gait phases (heel-off, toe-off, midswing, heel-strike). These values for each sound condition were then exported for statistical analyses. Peaks and footstep time intervals were extracted from the soundtrack wav files. Statistical analyses were conducted in R (version 4.3.1, R Core

Figure 4: Experiment 1 procedure.

Team, 2018) and, for Bayesian analysis, in JASP (version 0.19.3). Alpha levels were set at 0.05, with p-values adjusted for multiple comparisons, using Bonferroni correction. Non-parametric data (i.e., questionnaires) were analyzed using aligned rank transform ANOVAs (ART ANOVA [36]) with sound condition as the single factor, followed by Wilcoxon signed-rank tests when significant. Parametric data were analyzed using one-way ANOVAs with sound condition as the factor, with significant effects followed up by t-tests, also applying Bonferroni correction. For the Body Visualization data, participants' actual body weight was included as a covariate in the ANOVA to control for its influence on the body visualizer's weight scale values.

3.2 Results

We first report synchronization performance, as this was a prerequisite for the emergence of the illusion, followed by coordination performance across sound conditions. We then present results on the bodily illusion, including body feelings and emotional experience, body visualization and gait biomechanics.

3.2.1 Synchronization and Coordination Performance. Synchronization was assessed in two ways: alignment with the prerecorded footsteps in the soundtrack (synchronization to auditory cues) and alignment with a virtual 100 bpm metronome (synchronization to the underlying tempo used to generate the recordings). With regard to synchrony, there were no significant differences between sound conditions. The overall SD asynchrony mean(SE) value was 95.9(7.4) ms when synchronizing with the soundtracks, and 89.6(9.0) ms when synchronizing with the 100 bpm virtual metronome. These results indicate that participants synchronized reasonably well both with the auditory cues and with the underlying tempo, despite the outdoors experimental setup, as the SD asynchrony was below 100 ms [55]. In terms of coordination performance, the overall SD ISI mean(SE) value was 87.1(10.2) ms. We confirmed that there were no significant differences between sound conditions, regardless of the pitch alterations.

3.2.2 Body Feelings and Emotional Experience. Questionnaire data showed significant main effects of sound condition on *Weight* and *Dominance*, see Table 1 and Figure 5 a) and b). Participants reported feeling lighter in HF compared to LF and more dominant in HF than in LF and C. Effect sizes were large for both *Weight* and *Dominance* [22]. Importantly, no main effect was found for

Agency (i.e., the feeling of producing the sounds); follow-up and Bayesian analyses confirmed no differences between conditions, with participants consistently reporting moderate to high agency across all sound conditions. In other words, participants felt they were producing the sounds they heard across all conditions. Confirming preserved agency was important, as previous studies have shown that disruptions in agency can diminish sensory-induced body illusions [84, 149].

3.2.3 Body Visualization. ANOVA results showed that the main effect of sound condition was not significant ($F=2.29$, $p=0.113$). Overall, participants tended to represent their bodies as slimmer in HF than in LF (see Figure 5c). Furthermore, we found a significant interaction between sound condition and participants' actual body weight ($F=3.23$, $p=0.049$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.12$), medium effect size [22]). Consistent with [144], which employed real-time feedback, the effect of sound on perceived body weight was stronger for heavier participants, who showed larger differences between conditions—representing their body as wider/heavier in LF vs C and slimmer/lighter in HF vs C.

Additionally, we examined the individual data distribution and observed that one participant, only for this task, always reported their weight as greater than 120 kg, much higher than their actual weight. Because the extreme responses of this participant may have disproportionately increased variance, we conducted an exploratory sensitivity analysis excluding this individual. In that analysis—reported in the Supplementary Material—the effect of sound condition reached significance; however, we emphasize that our primary analysis includes all participants and that our conclusions are based solely on the full dataset.

3.2.4 Gait Biomechanics. Acceleration data revealed a significant effect of sound condition on downwards foot acceleration ($F=3.47$, $p=0.034$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.21$). Post hoc t-tests on z-scored data showed larger acceleration during the foot downward movement in LF than HF ($t=2.87$, $p=0.007$), as shown in Figure 5 d). Means (\pm SD) were HF: 0.48 (\pm 0.20), C: 0.51 (\pm 0.21) and LF: 0.58 (\pm 0.18). These results suggest that participants struck the ground with greater force and weight in LF compared to HF, which may be consistent with feeling heavier.

Experiment 1 showed that participants synchronized well with auditory cues and maintained a consistent walking rhythm despite the experimental setup and the variable conditions. Taken together,

Table 1: Effects of Sound Condition for questionnaire data (7-level Likert items except for 9-level valence, arousal and dominance scales). Median(Range) values and results of ANOVAs on aligned-ranked data, BF_{10} Bayes factors and Bonferroni- corrected Wilcoxon Pairwise Comparisons are shown.

Measure	ANOVA on aligned-rank transformed data			Wilcoxon Pairwise Comparisons		
	C HF LF (n)	Effect of Sound Condition	BF_{10}	HF vs LF	HF vs C	LF vs C
Valence	6.5(5) 7(5) 7(6)	$F=2.30, p=0.112, \eta_p^2=0.09$	0.69	$z=-1.68 p=0.092$	$z=-1.73 p=0.083$	$z=-0.14 p=0.891$
Arousal	3.5(8) 3(8) 3(8)	$F=1.25, p=0.296, \eta_p^2=0.05$	0.306	$z=-1.11 p=0.265$	$z=-1.34 p=0.179$	$z=-0.67 p=0.505$
Dominance	5(7) 6(7) 5(7)	$F=4.41, p=0.018, \eta_p^2=0.16$	2.87	$z=-2.16 p=0.031$	$z=-28 p=0.038$	$z=-0.07 p=0.943$
Quickness	4(7) 4(6) 4(6)	$F=0.88, p=0.422, \eta_p^2=0.04$	0.234	$z=-1.01 p=0.315$	$z=-0.67 p=0.505$	$z=-0.80 p=0.424$
Weight	3.5(6) 2.5(5) 4(6)	$F=4.26, p=0.020, \eta_p^2=0.16$	3.11	$z=-2.41 p=0.016$	$z=-1.82 p=0.069$	$z=-1.00 p=0.316$
Strength	4(5) 4.5(4) 4.5(6)	$F=0.24, p=0.788, \eta_p^2=0.01$	0.53	$z=-0.32 p=0.751$	$z=-0.55 p=0.585$	$z=-0.56 p=0.579$
Straightness	5(5) 5(5) 4(6)	$F=20, p=0.147, \eta_p^2=0.08$	0.848	$z=-1.43 p=0.153$	$z=-0.89 p=0.372$	$z=-1.42 p=0.157$
Masculinity	4(5) 4(6) 5(4)	$F=2.68, p=0.079, \eta_p^2=0.10$	1.179	$z=-2.13 p=0.033$	$z=-0.67 p=0.500$	$z=-1.66 p=0.097$
Agency	5(6) 5(6) 5(6)	$F=0.03, p=0.097, \eta_p^2=0.01$	0.122	$z=-0.25 p=0.800$	$z=-0.08 p=0.934$	$z=-0.26 p=0.792$
Vividness	4(5) 3(5) 4(6)	$F=0.37, p=0.694, \eta_p^2=0.02$	0.154	$z=-0.44 p=0.663$	$z=-0.24 p=0.812$	$z=-0.74 p=0.460$
Surprise	3(6) 3.5(6) 2(6)	$F=0.93, p=0.402, \eta_p^2=0.04$	0.235	$z=-1.06 p=0.288$	$z=-0.89 p=0.374$	$z=-0.18 p=0.860$
Proprioception	5(6) 6(5) 5(5)	$F=2.98, p=0.061, \eta_p^2=0.12$	1.221	$z=-1.72 p=0.085$	$z=-21 p=0.044$	$z=-0.49 p=0.625$

Figure 5: Experiment 1 Results. Questionnaire on Body Feelings and Emotional Experience items: a) Weight and b) Dominance. c) Visualized Body Weight Distortion; d) Downwards Foot Acceleration (denotes $p < .01$ and * $p < .05$).**

results also suggest that the Footsteps Illusion was effectively induced with a minimal setup using footstep soundtracks: in HF, participants felt lighter and more dominant, represented their bodies as slimmer, and struck the ground with less force than in LF. As in [144] we also found that the effects are shaped not only by the spectral qualities of the sounds but also by individual bodily characteristics such as body weight.

4 Experiment 2

Experiment 2 aimed to explore how the manipulated footstep sounds and environmental factors shape body perception and related behavior and emotional experience. To address these questions, a qualitative approach was adopted involving participant self-reflections obtained through interviews, and body mapping of embodied experiences. Participants could choose their own route in the experiment area.

4.1 Methods

4.1.1 Participants. The same subjects from Experiment 1, including the four previously excluded, participated in Experiment 2, leaving 28 participants (mean age \pm SD: 26.21 ± 9.99 years, range: 19-71; Sex: 13 males and 15 females; Gender: 13 masculine and 15

feminine; mean weight \pm SD: 66.86 ± 11.44 kg; mean height \pm SD: 170.25 ± 8.55 cm).

4.1.2 Procedure. Figure 6 shows a graphical overview of the experimental procedure.

After completing Experiment 1, participants were taken to a different part of the campus and told they could walk freely in the area while synchronizing their footsteps to an audio track of about five minutes. In contrast to Experiment 1 where participants only walked on a path made of concrete, in Experiment 2 participants were free to choose their walking path within an area that included grass, stone, tiles, concrete, and soil; see Figure 7 a). The only restrictions were not to leave the campus, not to enter buildings, and not to walk on the path of Experiment 1. There were two trials (LF, HF) with the order counterbalanced across participants.

For each trial, the audio was started where the participant wanted to begin their path. While the participant walked, the experimenter marked their trajectory on a landscape map; for an example, see Figure 7 b), also marking relevant information like interactions with people or weather. After completing both trials, a semi-structured interview was conducted about their experiences (see Supplementary Material for a list of questions). Participants reflected on the influence of environmental factors and soundtrack on their bodily

Figure 6: Experiment 2 procedure.

feelings, emotional experiences, and behavior, agency over the footstep sounds, and comparisons between Experiment 1 and 2. The landscape maps were used as an interview tool for participants to recall their experience and make comparisons between the two trials. Participants also added body map stickers where they depicted bodily and emotional experiences using colors, arrows, symbols, and words, as in [73, 74, 110, 162, 163].

4.1.3 Qualitative Analysis. Qualitative data from interviews was analyzed using Affinity Diagrams [10, 18, 60]. This process involves the following steps, which were followed for two research questions focused on gaining insights on how environmental factors interacted with the effects of sound on body perception, emotional experience and behavior, and how participants adapted to the synchronizing task in a varied environment, as well as its effects on their sense of agency and ownership over the sounds they heard. All the coders involved in the analysis had previous experience in qualitative coding, albeit at different levels. The main two authors of the paper had been previously involved in qualitative coding in other projects in the lab. One of them had been the main coder under the guidance of author 3 in a year-long project, and the other one had undertaken additional qualitative coding lessons. The main two authors were supervised by author 3 who is an expert in qualitative coding, with 10 years of experience.

- **Gathering Material:** All participant interviews were transcribed and separated into individual quotes, which were imported as post-its on Miro [103], a digital whiteboard.
- **Coding:** Relevant main ideas were extracted from the original quotes on the basis of the research question. The main two authors individually coded the post-its. They then compared their coding and author 3 was involved to solve any disagreements. This was a process of discussion and focused on whether the code captured all the relevant information related to the research question, the hierarchical organization of ideas, and the faithfulness to the original quote. For example, a quote from P18 was “*One bit that maybe did affect my ability to synchronize with the sound was going down the steps... I had to really synchronize after going up the steps... And kind of just going down the levels... I guess in general, I felt like a bit heavier footsteps going up than going down.*” For the research question on environmental factors, the coding agreed on was *steps/levels -> a) heavier footsteps going up than down and b) synchronize after going up steps*, whereas

for the question on synchronization, the coding agreed on was *going down steps really affected my ability to synchronize with sound -> had to really synchronize after going up steps.*

- **Grouping and Labeling:** The final codes were used, individually by the main two authors, to group and sort the data into categories based on their similarities or relationships.
- **Creating Hierarchy:** Along with author 3, common ideas were discussed and the groups were organized into further categories or themes, or smaller categories were merged together.

The resulting main themes for each question are discussed in the next section.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 Environmental Factors. Here, our main focus is on reporting interactions between environmental factors and sound condition on the study variables: bodily feelings, emotional experiences, and behavioral choices.

Built Environment: The built environment was considered an important factor because participants tried to match sounds (HF, LF) with the materiality of the surfaces. Some were “*looking for a space [to walk] that matched the sound*”, because they perceived the sound as being produced on a surface, like wood, and looked for a surface in the environment where their real footsteps could produce a similar sound. One type of surface that participants reflected on were *hard surfaces*, which several said matched the LF condition well, although they did not elaborate why. Participants had specific experiences with different surface materials:

- **Concrete:** In the HF condition, a few participants said they were less in harmony with the sound on the concrete or that the way of walking felt more forced, while there were others who said that the experience was more realistic walking on the concrete and they could “*make out that the sound I was hearing was very similar to the footsteps.*” [P20]. In LF, all participants who spoke about the concrete said that the sound matched the surface or that the contradiction with the sound they otherwise felt was less pronounced.
- **Stone:** One person who walked on stone in the HF condition said it was where the footstep sounds felt more like their own.

watching them, participants felt *"somewhat nervous"*, while not being observed made them feel *"stronger"*. This also depended on the sound condition. P11, for example, saw people watching him in the HF condition, but wasn't affected by people in LF. He explained that it was because in HF, his steps were different *"-The steps [I heard] were faster and more closed. I couldn't open my legs as much, they were closer together...like a zigzag,"* and this way of walking made him more feminine and stylized, and stand out *"-I don't know what they were thinking, but I saw them looking... [my walk] was faster, more feminine... and everyone walked more relaxed and slower."*

Finally, some participants connected their *spatial choices* to the presence of other people. Some participants felt more comfortable being around people in HF than LF. P13 said, *"-Well [in HF], I dared to walk closer to other people, but [in LF] I didn't. I don't know, it makes me less anxious, I think... because the sound made me feel less trapped."* P15 also described how he felt like he embodied two different characters in the two sound conditions – in HF he was a *"posh, skinny, young man with a trench coat, shoulder pads, hands in pockets, of a certain status, and felt important"* who approached people more but looked at them less. And in LF, he was a *"fat, hunched, older man walking slowly"* who approached people less but looked at them more.

Further insights on the relationship between environmental factors and body perception. We obtained results on how participants felt that environmental factors influenced their bodily feelings, emotional experiences, and behavioral choices, *irrespective of sound*. We bring these illustrative results because, although our interest in this paper lies in the relationship body-sound-environment, they can inform future research, as we will reflect on in the discussion. Some participants experienced that the materiality of the surfaces affected their body perception irrespective of the sound, e.g., how much they could feel certain body parts. For example, few participants walking on hard surfaces said that they could feel their feet more due to the rough texture and reflected on the feeling of the foot hitting the hard ground: *"-The step is harder, it went straighter, more directly to the place."* [P25]. Similarly, some participants felt that texture of the grass itself affected the way they walked. Some felt that their feet were sinking, and had to rush to keep up with the pace of the audio. This was not experienced by everyone: few felt themselves to be faster in the grass.

Participants also experienced the weather to affect their emotional experience and movement. For example, in the cold, one participant wanted to walk faster but could not due to the synchronization task, and another one said that their steps felt lighter and slower in comparison to the audio when they were in the sun, and another stopped paying attention to step speed while enjoying the warmth. Finally, several participants noted both the environmental sounds in the recording and those around them. Some could not distinguish between the two. Social sounds like conversations were distracting, while natural sounds—especially birds—were relieving or drew them toward greenery. In contrast, traffic noises felt overwhelming.

4.2.2 Synchronization and Agency. One of our main objectives with Experiment 2 was to understand the interaction of contextual factors with the sound conditions and the impact this would have on the experience of the Footsteps Illusion. To this end, we were

interested in participants' reflections on their capacity or not to execute the synchronization task when their activity was variable, and their feeling of agency over the footstep sounds, as this is known to be necessary to experience an illusion [40, 84].

Synchronization: In general, participants found the synchronization task easy, but described certain moments where they found it more challenging. Several participants reflected on factors that *facilitated or impeded* their synchronization. Among the factors that facilitated the synchronization was the fact that participants could choose their own path *"-[In Experiment 1], when you turn you have to synchronize again. [In Experiment 2] there is freedom. That is, when you are already immersed in the steps, you turn, or when it's more natural."* [P10]. In fact, there was only one participant, P22, who mentioned that they found synchronizing easier in Experiment 1 because they were *"-totally focused on following the steps."* For some people, what helped was practice *"-The first time it had caught me off guard, but the second time I was better prepared to follow the steps as they sounded."* [P07].

On the other hand, there were various factors that impeded accurate synchronization with the footstep sounds. One was speed: at least one third of the participants mentioned that the speed of the footsteps in the recording was slower than the pace at which they usually walked. *"-It was difficult for me because I walk very fast and [to synchronize] I had to slow down."* [P21].

Similarly, some participants found that environmental factors, such as type of surface, presence of levels, type of path, or the necessity to turn or climb also presented impediments to accurate synchronization. For example, P06 said they found their movement less harmonious on the concrete *"-it was harder...less automatic and clumsier,"* while P01 said it was difficult to synchronize on the grass because *"-I was kicking the leaves and everything."* Several participants described that going up or down steps posed challenges. P12 summed it up well saying, *"-[Synchronizing] was easy, except when I had to turn or I came across someone or an obstacle."*

Another common challenge for synchronization was that participants were getting distracted from the task. This was either because they got lost in thoughts, someone spoke to them, or because of the background noise in the audio.

Soundtrack errors were also elements that impeded synchronization. A few participants remarked on issues in the soundtrack that made synchronizing difficult such as a *"limp"*, a *"stumble"*, or breaks in the recording.

Participants reported on several *strategies* that they used to be able to synchronize themselves with the sound when walking:

- **Adaptation to speed:** Some participants mentioned that they perceived the velocity of the steps changing during the soundtrack. One participant waited for the pace to return to normal and continue, and several adapted their pace, going faster or slower to match the audio.
- **Choose types of movement/paths:** A few participants said they tried to turn as little as possible, or to walk on straight, wide paths in order to synchronize better.
- **Footstep phases:** P04 explained how some steps had three phases and to synchronize well, he tried to follow the middle phase *"-The first step sounded like it had three phases. I understand that these would be: support, plant, and release. But*

it sounded like three quick steps. And then you could hear the second step, a clean one... It was like when a horse runs, that the first step you hear the three and then one. I was trying to keep up with the middle step of the three that came first."

Agency: There were people who felt like the steps they heard were their own and others who did not. The main reasons people did not feel agency over the steps were the speed "*–[The steps] felt more imposed, you have to follow the steps of another person...the rhythm is so slow so it's difficult for me to think that those steps could be mine.*" [P04], and the sound – "*–My steps wouldn't sound like this... the sound was like that of heels or a kind of shoe that produces sound. I always use sports shoes that don't make that much noise.*" [P16]. P25 distinguished between agency, or the feeling that you are generating the sounds you hear, and ownership, or the feeling of ownership over the body you are hearing "*–They were like another person's steps, but at the same time my feet. They are my feet but not my sound.*" P28 said that they could ascribe the footsteps to themselves because they happened at the same moment, "*–but at the same time, I didn't feel like myself because it's not my way of walking.*" For a couple of other participants, feeling agency or not was a question of concentration "*–I felt like I was producing the sounds when I was focused, but if my mind was a bit more scattered, I didn't.*" [P27]. Most people who mentioned not feeling like they were producing the sounds said the footsteps sounded like another person, referring to "*the person in the audio*" doing something different from them. However, a few people said they felt like they were simply synchronizing to a sound or soundtrack.

5 Discussion

In the following sections, we discuss the study findings, focusing on insights from the synchronization task and how they relate to the Footsteps Illusion, as well as the influence of environmental factors. In addition, we reflect on the methodological challenges and opportunities of research on 'body transformation' wearable technologies in real-world studies and introduce methodological tools to advance this line of research.

5.1 Synchronizing Walking to Prerecorded Pitch-Altered Footsteps Influenced Body Perception, Gait and Emotional Experience

Our results show that participants were able to synchronize their walking with the prerecorded footstep soundtracks, demonstrating that the task was feasible. This substantiates prior work, showing that people can reliably synchronize gait with auditory cues such as music tempo [32, 61] or a metronome [40], in outdoor spaces. Although synchronization in our study was less precise than in controlled lab-based tasks (e.g., [32, 40, 61]), this can be explained by the outdoor setting—with its natural distractors and irregular walking surfaces—as well as the use of prerecorded footsteps, with inherent small imperfections (e.g., a "*limp*" or "*stumble*"), unlike metronome beats (see [106]). Importantly, the measured asynchronies remained within acceptable ranges [55], confirming that the pace of the soundtracks was easy to follow. Participants could adapt their gait across different surfaces, although some reported the pace felt slower than their natural speed, requiring adjustments that sometimes felt unnatural.

Previous research has shown that surface materials such as concrete, grass, or soil affect gait patterns and speed [67, 120]. Our results extend this by showing that participants maintained a consistent rhythm across variable outdoor conditions, even when listening to pitch-altered footsteps (HF and LF), which are typically associated with lighter, faster steps and slower, heavier steps, respectively. This suggests that synchronizing to the sounds partly overrode environmental influences, in line with [45], who found that music can mask environmental effects on walking speed. Yet, our qualitative reports show participants did notice surface effects: for instance, they felt their feet more on hard concrete, which helped them maintain pace, whereas sinking into grass required them to rush to keep up with the soundtrack. Thus, participants balanced environmental constraints with the synchronization demand.

The ability to align one's actions with the auditory cues also reinforced participants' sense of agency [84]. Across conditions, they reported moderate to high agency scores, indicating they attributed the sounds to their own actions—an important condition for sensory-driven illusions of the body, as shown in neuroscience [62, 63, 157] and related HCI works [31, 57, 130, 131]. They also reported high proprioceptive awareness, suggesting that hearing manipulated footsteps did not interfere with their ability to localize their feet.

Crucially, our study provides the first evidence that the Footsteps Illusion can be elicited while synchronizing to prerecorded pitch-altered footsteps, rather than relying on real-time feedback. Participants perceived their bodies as lighter in HF and heavier in LF, replicating earlier lab findings [139, 144]. These effects appeared both in self-reports and in a body visualization task, and were modulated by participants' actual weight, with heavier participants experiencing the illusion more strongly, as in [144]. This demonstrates that actively synchronizing one's movements to external auditory cues can alter body perception, consistent with prior work on the enfacement illusion using tactile synchronization [142].

Beyond body weight perception, synchronization also influenced behavior and emotional experience. Participants struck the ground with greater force (i.e., applied more weight) in LF compared to HF, consistent with a heavier perceived weight in LF, and reported greater dominance in HF. These effects are novel. While previous studies on the Footsteps Illusion, involving both chronic pain (CPRS) patients [140] and people with eating disorders [24] have shown feelings of increased perceived emotional dominance for LF, in this work participants have reported these feelings in HF. Evidence of this was found both from the questionnaire in Experiment 1 as in the interviews: P15 mentioned that the character he embodied in HF perceived himself as important and of a certain status, and was more open to approaching people; P13 added feeling less trapped. This difference from the other exclusively in-lab studies [24, 140] could be associated with social factors and feeling in control, less awkward. In [40], hearing distinct yet synchronous footsteps from others increased participants' feelings of dominance; here, one may speculate that in our setup participants also experienced walking in synchrony with another person, and that a greater distinctiveness of self-other sounds in HF could have contributed to higher dominance scores. Additionally, some participants reported that in HF they listened more closely to themselves than to the outside world, and this may have contributed to a greater sense of control

or dominance over the situation. There are some body perception changes findings, as well as emotional changes, that were shown in previous studies, see [21, 24], e.g., quickness, masculinity and emotional valence but were not replicated in this work. This could be related both to the outdoor setup and to the smaller sample size compared to [24]. Importantly, the main variable targeted by the illusion—perceived body weight—was significantly altered by the sound manipulation.

Overall, our findings demonstrate that prerecorded footsteps provide a minimal setup—requiring only a smartphone or audio player and headphones—that makes it possible to elicit the Footsteps Illusion in real-world environments. This opens up opportunities to conduct studies in everyday contexts (e.g., clinical, home, outdoors), with broader participant groups and over longer periods of time. Such approaches hold promise for advancing research on the malleability of body perception and its effects on behavior and emotion, as well as for developing applications to support people across diverse contexts and needs [50, 140, 141, 144].

5.2 Taking the Study Outside the Lab: Contextual Factors Shaping the Sound-driven Experience

Participants' experiences of the Footsteps Illusion—which involves perceiving sounds and their effects on body perception, behavior and emotional experience—were deeply shaped by environmental and contextual factors. This aligns with prior HCI research highlighting the interplay between body, space, and materiality [59, 73, 74, 95, 136, 147, 152, 159, 162].

The campus environment, with its variety of surface materials, enabled insights on the kinds of surfaces participants were drawn to in the different sound conditions. Some described certain surfaces as *"matching"* or *"being harmonious"* with the sounds, like hard surfaces with LF. Other said they could *"walk like the sound"* on different surfaces, though responses were varied: some felt they could walk like LF on soil, one could do so on grass, and another felt the footsteps more like their own on the stone in HF. Since, to our knowledge, no prior studies have examined walking on varied surfaces while listening to prerecorded pitch-altered footsteps, future work that systematically controls walking paths is needed to disentangle specific sound-surface interactions. Virtual surface simulations, such as sound augmented sandals [159] or vibrotactile augmented sandals [172] used to reproduce surfaces like asphalt or grass, could provide valuable tools here.

Further, several participants also reported that the *type of space* influenced their experience. For instance, during LF, some participants sought out closed and darker spaces, as these felt more congruent with the sound. Prior research supports such cross-modal implicit associations between pitch and spatial meaning (high frequency as 'open', low frequency as 'closed' [165]), elevation (high frequency as 'up', low frequency as 'down' [29]) and illumination [79, 82] (high frequency as bright illuminated environments, LF as dark [17, 170]). These associations often draw from the statistics of natural auditory scenes. For example, HF sounds are more strongly absorbed by surfaces than LF [38], meaning that in closed spaces the sound reaching the listener contains proportionally more LF than in open outdoor environments. The same

applies to the mapping between pitch and elevation, which has also been shown in natural auditory scenes [90]. A limitation of our study is that varied walking paths across HF and LF conditions prevent direct comparison of situations, between the two conditions. For instance, in HF one participant described their steps as feeling lighter when walking in the sun, but we do not have a corresponding LF comparison. Yet, in cases like this, where participants did not specifically report an interaction with sound, prior work linking HF with lightness [79, 82] suggests that sound may have influenced bodily experience. Similarly, prior work showing how the (acoustically) perceived size of the space influences emotional responses to sound events [135] suggests that the association between LF and closed spaces may interact with emotional experience. Carefully controlled future studies are needed to disentangle the effects of environmental factors and sound on bodily and emotional experiences.

The relationship and emotional attitude towards the presence of other people was also found to be modulated by the sound condition. Participants described approaching others more readily in HF, but not in LF. One explained that HF made them feel *"less trapped"*, consistent with HF's associations with openness, as well as dominance (see previous section). This resonates with recent work on *Audio Personas* [151], which shows that self-anchored sounds in AR that reflect one's own current state (e.g., rain sounds to depict a bad mood) can alter social perception and interactions, with positive audio personas being perceived as more likable and less threatening than negative audio personas. Similarly, P15 described embodying different personas depending on the sound: in HF, a *"posh, important, skinny, young man with a trench coat and shoulder pads who went near people but didn't look at them much"*, and in LF *"a fat, hunched older man who stayed away from people but observed them more"*. This opens a new line of questioning about links between acoustic features and perceived age. The sounds produced by one's body (e.g., the voice) change in pitch across the lifespan [126], and acoustic manipulations can facilitate the embodiment of virtual bodies of a different age than one's own [138]. Since postures and movement also vary with age [89, 173], and are influenced by sound [144], these findings point to a rich new direction for research. In the present study, some participants also described how the sound influenced their movement and body perception, which in turn affected how they believed others might perceive them, as described below.

Acoustic properties of footsteps are also known to affect perceived gender identity: LF is associated with more masculine, heavier walkers, and HF with more feminine, lighter walkers wearing high heels [75, 153]. The Footsteps Illusion itself has been shown to temporarily shift gender identity [21, 24, 144]. In our study, many participants noted that HF sounded like *"heels on a hard ground"*, which incidentally made it difficult for them to find a corresponding surface, especially since they were asked to wear sports shoes. When walking in grass with HF, for some this mismatch between the sound of "hard heels" and the soft surface underfoot highlighted the artificiality of the sounds, while others still reported feeling lighter or more relaxed. The perception of a high heel sound was also generalized to changes towards a more feminine gait and body perception due to the sound. For example, a male participant described walking faster, with a more feminine, stylized stride,

crossing his legs as he walked, while a female participant reported walking more “*from the hips*” in HF but feeling more masculine in her shoulders. Prior work has shown gender differences in gait biomechanics depending on surface type, with implications for pedometer accuracy [67], with lower accuracy for females, especially while walking on a soft surface (dry beach sand), which they attribute to possible surface-induced changes in lower-limb gait biomechanics. Together, these results suggest that both surface and sound independently shape gendered experiences and gait; further studies are necessary to understand how these factors interact.

5.3 Methodological Reflections, Limitations and Future Work

Since our study had two main goals (replicating the Footsteps Illusion outdoors with a minimal setup, and understanding the role of contextual factors in interaction with sound to affect bodily and emotional experiences and behavior), it was necessary to make methodological choices at the level of stimulus creation, prototype design, experimental approach, and appropriate measures for evaluation. A quantitative approach allowed us to maintain a level of control in Experiment 1, making our results directly comparable to previous in-lab work, and validating the efficacy of our minimal device more objectively. On the other hand, a qualitative approach allowed us to gain detailed accounts of participants’ experiences with the sound in a varied environment. These insights offered nuance, reasoning, and possible individual differences imperative to future design processes and often missed in purely quantitative data [109]. Future work could incorporate quantitative measures during the open walks to be able to compare conditions and understand the efficacy of the illusion when participants move freely.

Our design process involved considered decisions at various stages, which contributed to the replicability of the illusion. For example, recording with walkers in different weight ranges allowed us to recruit participants of different weights, using corresponding soundtracks for each participant, possibly contributing to high agency scores across participants. A piloting process helped select between the footstep soundtracks, making the final soundtracks as contextually relevant as possible. We also added environmental sounds recorded on site; some participants reported not knowing whether specific noises (e.g., birds or traffic) came from the headphones or the real environment. While this speaks in favor of ecological validity, it also distracted some participants from the synchronization task. This is an important consideration on including a synchronization task that differs from the original Footsteps Illusion where participants hear their own footsteps modified in real time. Future work should examine how attention influences both synchronization and sound effects, especially given that real-world distractions can affect attentional focus and the intention to synchronize [69]. Similarly, using natural recordings of human walkers produced realistic soundtracks but introduced small imperfections (e.g., a “*limp*” or “*stumble*”). The predetermined pace of 100 bpm was not optimal for all participants; in future work, tailoring playback speed to individuals’ preferred pace would likely enhance ecological validity and engagement. Moreover, although we hypothesized that participants did not exhibit asymmetries in their walking, adding an accelerometer to each ankle in future studies could provide more

accurate synchronization measures. Additionally, this focused on validating the synchronization procedure under controlled conditions. In Experiment 1 participants walked on a single surface and at a single speed, however introducing measures of gait features involving different variables, i.e. walking surfaces, speeds and also footwear, sets forth an important direction for future research.

Prerecorded footstep sounds, as the ones we have presented, also offer possibilities for HCI researchers and developers. They could be used in wearable devices that employ sonification techniques [8, 9, 53, 73, 88, 110, 114, 115, 128, 167] to sonify footsteps [15, 49, 159, 168] enabling more natural ‘foot augmentation’ applications [37]. Such devices could trigger pitch-altered footsteps in response to actual gait phases, supporting studies in everyday contexts (e.g., clinical, home, outdoors), with larger and more diverse participant groups over longer periods. This would also help mitigate novelty or shyness effects observed here. More generally, the footsteps sound database is positioned as a valuable tool (see other sound databases [44, 129]) for future applications in rehabilitation, psychological interventions or as a training dataset for artificial recognition systems as [54].

As the first study to take the Footsteps Illusion outside the lab, we developed the landscape mapping tool, inspired by [4], to capture situated experiences. This proved crucial for documenting how bodily sensations shifted with textures, weather, and social contexts. Together with body mapping, this provided a multidimensional view of how sound interacts with environment and space to shape body perception.

At the same time, limitations must be acknowledged. In this study, our main focus was on evaluating the effective induction of the Footsteps Illusion rather than the usability or user experience of the device. Although setup time was short (under five minutes), some participants reported that the equipment felt obstructive or interfering in their walking experience, and suggested using wireless headphones. Future work should incorporate usability metrics such as portability and comfort to evaluate and better understand the device experience alongside the illusion. Additionally, our study was conducted in an urban area, and although Experiment 2 included different surface materials (grass, stone, concrete), future research should explore more varied environments, broader age ranges, and potential cultural differences that may affect, for example, interaction with others. We did not directly compare in-lab versus outdoor conditions; however, significant differences between HF and LF in perceived body weight confirm that body perception was modulated while synchronizing to prerecorded sounds. Future studies should directly test whether the illusion operates at the same level as with real-time feedback. Furthermore, we acknowledge the limitation of comparability and generalizable insights on contextual factors due to lack of control outside the lab. Although the study took not more than two months to complete, the time of year, its associated conditions including the number of other people present on campus, and other resulting factors were beyond our control. This lack of control is inherent to in-the-wild research, which seeks to understand technology interventions in everyday life [111]. Still, taking the study outdoors revealed new lines of inquiry that would not have emerged in a lab, including sound–surface interactions, sound–social dynamics, links between acoustic features and perceived age or posture, and interactions between sound, surface,

and gender. Both controlled and in-the-wild studies are needed to isolate the role of these variables and their interaction with sound.

Because sound-driven body modulation can influence emotional states and bodily self-perception, it is important to consider potential safety implications when deploying such systems in real-world contexts. The sound levels were calibrated to replicate a realistic auditory environment—background and footstep sounds were adjusted to typical real-world levels—thereby excluding the possibility of hearing damage or discomfort and ensuring that the auditory cues remained natural and non-intrusive. Altered body perception may shift attention inwards, reducing external focus and potentially affecting confidence or gait, which could be critical in environments requiring heightened situational awareness (e.g., uneven terrain). To mitigate such risks, future work could include asking participants about their familiarity with walking while wearing headphones, as previous research shows that headphone use can influence spatial awareness and perceived safety.

Finally, although we borrow the title of this work from Lou Reed's iconic song, we emphasize that our study does not address the themes of the song. Some readers may consider this a misuse of the original work. Yet, given that several studies have explored gender perceptions in body illusions [132, 133], including work on the Footsteps Illusion [21, 24, 144], we hope the playful reference highlights rather than detracts from the broader conversation about identity, perception, and sound.

5.4 Novelty and Contributions

In Sections 5.1 and 5.2 of this discussion, we have reflected in detail on how concrete insights from our study align with, extend or challenge those in previous works. Here, we reflect more broadly on the core contributions and novelty of our work.

First, we provide evidence that the Footsteps Illusion can be replicated with prerecorded sounds. We have found that the effects on perceived body weight reported in previous Footsteps Illusion studies [24, 139, 144], and its related effects on body behavior and emotional experience, can be elicited when participants synchronize with prerecorded pitch-altered footstep sounds, rather than relying on real-time feedback. This finding is significant because it demonstrates the possibility of inducing the Footsteps Illusion with minimal setups in complex interactional settings outside the lab. It paves the way for future studies on how sound interactions modulate body perception in complex in-the-wild contexts and investigate their effects over longer periods of time—both promising research areas that have only recently begun to be explored [50, 73, 161]. Beyond perceptual validation, our findings point to several application domains where this sound-based modulation of body perception can inform design. Lightweight auditory manipulations that induce feelings of lightness, strength, or stability could support well-being and rehabilitation contexts, such as assistive walking programs or physiotherapy routines to motivate movement, reinforce motor patterns, or support confidence during gait retraining (e.g., gait rehabilitation for stroke survivors [50]). Other clinical applications could include interventions for populations who experience bodily heaviness, like individuals with depressive symptomatology [46]. The Footsteps Illusion has shown potential benefits for other clinical conditions which are known

to be accompanied by feelings of heaviness, like in people with complex regional pain syndrome [140]. Further, the illusion may also help reveal anomalous mechanisms of sensory integration of bodily information in people with eating disorders (see [141]), with our minimal setup offering opportunities to study these conditions in real-life contexts. In interactive performance, the minimal setup enables new embodied experiences in dance, theater, and immersive installations, where performers or audiences can explore shifting body sensations through sound-driven transformations [34, 110]. More broadly, our results provide design guidelines for systems aiming to steer body perception—showing that even simple, pre-recorded audio can reliably modulate felt physicality. Explicitly connecting these perceptual outcomes to sound design strategies opens avenues for CHI researchers and practitioners to develop interventions that shape bodily experience in everyday environments, from physical activity and sports to artistic expression.

We contribute a novel prototype to enable this type of in-the-wild studies. The prototype incorporates a minimal and portable version of the Footsteps Illusion, thus extending previous technical solutions that relied on more complex sensors and sound modifications on-the-fly [24, 139].

Further, we also contribute insights on how different contextual factors in outdoor environments, i.e., surface material or presence of other people, interact with sound in shaping body perception and user experience. To the best of our knowledge, our study is the first of its kind investigating the interplay of alterations of bodily sounds, contextual factors, and body perception. Previous studies have often focused on dyads, e.g., impact of contextual factors (e.g., [4, 78]), or sound modulations (e.g., [15, 119, 137]) alone on body perception. Our work opens new avenues to investigate the malleability of body perception in relation to sound and environment.

Additionally, our paper presents two smaller contributions. First, a novel spatial mapping tool (i.e., a landscape map) consisting of context-sensitive body maps anchored in the environment, which help capture relationships between body and environment. These serve to address recent calls for better documentation tools that capture the complexity of lived experience, particularly in regards to the body's interaction with others and with the environment [4, 160]. Second, we provide a database of prerecorded footstep sounds, which can be utilized as a resource for other applications, i.e., sound design and virtual reality; and for other studies in the area.

Finally, our work highlights the need for further studies conducted outside of the laboratory. By exploring this illusion in real-world contexts, we open new research questions that can later be brought back to the lab, where we can systematically examine the influence of specific factors under controlled conditions. In this study, we focused on the Footstep Illusion as a case study; however, researchers are welcome to apply this framework to other studies.

Although previous work has demonstrated that auditory manipulation can alter body perception, our study clarifies and extends the scope of contributions in two complementary ways. First, we replicate and validate core effects of the Footsteps Illusion by showing that changes in perceived body weight—and their related influences on gait and emotional experience—emerge in outdoor environments. Second, we introduce several novel contributions that advance this line of research beyond prior work: we validate core

effects of the Footsteps Illusion when participants synchronize their walking with prerecorded pitch-altered footsteps, showing that the illusion is robust even when real-time manipulation of the sounds produced by the individuals is removed; a fully deployable, minimal prototype suitable for in-the-wild studies; new methodological tools for capturing situated bodily experiences (landscape maps and body mapping); and an analysis of how contextual factors shape synchronization, agency, and body perception in real-world settings. Together, these elements establish a lightweight and scalable research paradigm that both reproduces established findings and expands the technical, ecological, and methodological possibilities for studying and designing sound-driven body transformations.

6 Conclusion

This work explored the potential effects of walking in synchrony with pitch-altered footstep sounds on body perception and examined the robustness of the Footsteps Illusion in outdoor, real-world contexts beyond controlled laboratory conditions. The goal was to better understand whether, and how, contextual and environmental factors shape the illusion's effects. Across two experiments, the results confirmed that, even during a synchronization task with prerecorded footstep sounds, pitch-altered footsteps influenced participants' body perception, behavior, and emotional experience. This effect emerged consistently, despite the experiments being conducted with different setups, under varying environmental conditions, and along diverse walking paths chosen by participants. Such consistency suggests a robust influence of auditory feedback on body perception. Further, our study provided insights into how environmental factors outside the lab—i.e., walking surface or the presence of other people—interact with sound in shaping body perception and user experience. In addition to these findings, this work contributes novel tools for studying multisensory body perception in everyday contexts: (1) a minimal, portable prototype that enables experiencing the Footsteps Illusion [24, 139, 144] in outdoor settings; (2) a spatial mapping tool with context-sensitive body maps to capture relationships between body and environment; and (3) a database of prerecorded footstep sounds that can serve as a resource for other applications. Together, these contributions open new avenues for designing and investigating sound-based body transformation experiences in everyday settings, with potential applications in diverse fields, including health, sports, entertainment, and the arts.

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